

F.No. P-16/4/2022-Estt-A&C-AC_AN/ 352
अंडमान तथा निकोबार प्रशासन
Andaman & Nicobar Administration
कला एवं संस्कृति निदेशालय
Directorate of Art and Culture

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Address
National Memorial Cellular Jail Complex
Atlanta Point, Port Blair - 744 101
Andaman & Nicobar Islands, INDIA

Port Blair, Dated 30th June, 2023

To

Shri.Kamanuru Kiran Kumar,
D.No. 20/1042 Kondadibba Kondadibba,
Nellore, Andhra Pradesh.
nir.kirankk@gmail.com.

Sub:- CPGRAM regarding changing name of Port Blair: Reg.

Sir,

I am directed to refer to your Grievance No. GOVAN/E/2023/0000151 dated 09.06.2023 on the subject cited above and to furnish the information as follows-

Sl. No.	Query	Reply
1	Please change the name of Capital of Andaman & Nicobar Islands, as Port Blair is a British name, so my request is to give it a name related to our India. Hope you can consider my request.	This shall be examined and further decision if any will be informed in due course.

Yours faithfully

30/06/23

Assistant Director (Art & Culture)

6
30.06.2023

No. U-13015/1/2018-ANL (Part-I)
Government of India (Bharat Sarkar)
Ministry of Home Affairs (Grih Mantralaya)

North Block, New Delhi
Dated, the 13th September, 2024

To,

The Chief Secretary,
UT of A&N Administration,
UT Secretariat, Port Blair

Subject: Approval of proposal from the UT of Andaman and Nicobar Administration for renaming of Port Blair as "Sri Vijaya Puram". -reg.

Sir,

I am directed to refer to UT of A&N Administration's letter No. M/10/2023-Estt-A&C-AC_AN-Part(1) dated 11.09.2024 on the subject cited above and to convey the approval of the competent authority on the proposal of the UT of Andaman and Nicobar Administration to rename "Port Blair" as "Sri Vijaya Puram". Hindi version of the name is "श्री विजयपुरम".

2. A&NI Administration is requested to take further necessary action in the matter and submit compliance report to this Ministry at the earliest.

Yours faithfully,

13/09/24

(S.K. Sudhakar)

Under Secretary to the Govt. of India

Tel. No. 23093575